

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 3.1.

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

Stakeholder engagement plan

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
AE4EU	CSA Agroecology for Europe
CBP	Capacity Building Program
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
LL	Living Lab
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing committee on agricultural research
WP	Work package
WP1	ALL-Ready work package on vision and mission of the network
WP2	ALL-Ready work package on mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms for carrying out participatory agroecological research and innovation including KPI's for the network
WP3	ALL-Ready work package on Coordination of stakeholder engagement and the ALL-Ready pilot
WP4	ALL-Ready work package on implementation and sustainability of the network
WP5	ALL-Ready work package on capacity building
WP6	ALL-Ready work package on knowledge and data Management
WP7	ALL-Ready work package on communication and dissemination
WP8	ALL-Ready work package on communication and dissemination

Introduction

ALL-Ready (Grant Agreement Number 101000349) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will support agroecology (agroecology) transition throughout Europe. Based on the premise that AE can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, this network will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that farming systems are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity and degradation of soil and water quality. As described in D1.1 (Mambrini-Doudet et al., 2021), the network would promote transdisciplinary, highly participatory, inclusive and coordinated experimentation in real life settings, ensure knowledge exchange at EU level, and the delivery of series of long-term data on ecological processes applied to agriculture in diverse conditions across the EU. It would support farmers – at farm, landscape and regional level - in understanding and implementing agroecological practices at the scale needed for significant positive economic, environmental and social impact.

Since ALL-Ready prepares the framework for this future European network as a community of AE LLs and RIs, the 'LL' approach is integrated in the project by relying on multi-stakeholder engagement during all WPs. WP3 is responsible for the overall coordination of stakeholder engagement during the ALL-Ready project. Involving stakeholders from the start of the process of preparing the future network in Europe will ensure that it will satisfy stakeholder's needs and is built upon their experiences, knowledge and motivation. The objective of the stakeholder engagement plan is to guarantee a coordination and alignment of stakeholder engagement during the activities of the other work packages.

This document outlines detailed information on stakeholder engagement activities within the ALL-Ready project. In what follows, the importance of a bottom-up approach in preparing a framework for a future European network of LL/RI for AE transition will be elaborated, taking into account the challenges when engaging a diversity of stakeholders (chapter 1). In the second part, an overview of stakeholder groups that will be engaged along the process will be provided. For each of these stakeholder groups, it is described how they might be affected by this network and how they can contribute to its development. Based on this, a draft stakeholder engagement plan is provided at the end of chapter 2, which is mainly derived from the different activities described in the project proposal. However, as stakeholder engagement is something that cannot be fixed in advance, the actual process of involvement will be described in detail in a final chapter 3.

1. Bottom-up approach for a European-wide network of LLs and RIs on agroecology:

1.1 Stakeholder engagement as a key prerequisite

The overall goal of the project is to develop a framework for a future European network of LLs and RIs to support the transition to AE.

RIs are open research facilities for experimentation at different scales (plot, farm, landscape level and networks). They are expected to contribute to bringing of corpus of knowledge for AE transition and are expected to have a central role in education, in providing data to stakeholders, and provide services in an open science vision (D1.1: Mambrini-Doudet at al., 2021).

LLs can be defined as practice-driven organisations that facilitate and foster innovation, as well as real-life environments or arenas where both open innovation and user innovation processes can be studied and subject to experiments and where new solutions are developed (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>). Three basic operational principles to support LL activities are i) co-creation, ii) user-centered, iii) in real life conditions (D1.1: Mambrini-Doudet at al., 2021). These characteristics suggest that co-creation processes are only possible with the participation of stakeholders.

In this project, we aim at implementing these basic operational principles in developing the framework for the future network. In order to co-create this framework, the project relies on a **multi-stakeholder approach and end-user involvement** from the early start of the process. Many definitions of 'stakeholder' are circulating. In this document however, there will be relied on Freeman (1984) defining stakeholders as '*any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the project's objectives*'.

Involving stakeholders throughout this process will:

Capture knowledge: ensure to include stakeholder's needs by building upon their experiences, knowledge and motivation. Stakeholder engagement will help to capture information and perspectives from a wide range of sources, providing a more robust knowledge base from which to build our framework for the future network.

Understand added value to a diversity of stakeholders: different stakeholders hold different values and consequently judge the value of such a network in diverse ways. The purpose of stakeholder engagement in this context is to identify and understand the diverse needs and expectations. As this network concerns a European-wide network, it is important to capture regional and local needs and conditions, in order to ensure that the network is responsive to the needs across all European regions.

Increase ownership: Stakeholder engagement in co-creation processes is also linked to enhancing the sense of ownership. This is considered important for the long-term success of the future network and. Thus, incorporating the concern for durability of the network is one of the criteria for its success.

1.2 Different levels of stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder involvement in this project means to give stakeholders the opportunity to participate in the process of developing the framework/network. Throughout this process, we can distinguish between different levels of stakeholder involvement or participation.

Different typologies or levels of participation have been described by multiple authors. A review of typologies is summarised in figure 1. These include mainly typologies specifically developed for use in the public sector. In this project, the participation typology of Wilcox (1994) is used, because it allows enough detail and is easy to understand. Furthermore, its applicability can easily be extended and adapted to our particular effort to develop a framework for a future network of LLs and RIs. Five levels of participation can be distinguished in the typology of Wilcox but in this project, the first four levels of participation are considered.

Informing: informing stakeholders about the ongoing process without giving them the opportunity to intervene.

Consulting: offering options to stakeholders, listening to their feedback, but not allowing new ideas.

Involving (deciding together in Figure 1): encouraging additional options and ideas, and providing opportunities for joint decision making.

Collaborating (acting together in Figure 1): not only different stakeholders deciding together, but also forming a partnership to carry it out.

Empowering (supporting in Figure 1): offering funds, advice or other support to stakeholders to develop their own agendas within guidelines.

Community					Risk Management	Company
Amstein (1969)	Dorsey <i>et al.</i> (1994)	Wilcox (1994)	Pretty & Shah (1994)	UNDP (1997)	Fischoff (1998)	
Citizen control	Ongoing involvement	Supporting	Self mobilisation	Self-management	All of below	Decisional
Delegated power	Seek consensus		Interactive participation	Partnership	All we have to do is make them partners	
Partnership	Test ideas, seek advice	Acting together		Risk-sharing	All we have to do is treat them nice	
Placation	Define issues	Deciding together	Functional participation	Decision-making	All we have to do is show them it's a good deal for them	Consultative
Consultation	Consult on reactions		Participation by consultation	Consensus-building	All we have to do is show them that they've accepted similar risks in the past	
Informing	Gather info perspectives	Consultation	Participation by information giving	Consultation	All we have to do is explain what we mean by the numbers	Informative
Therapy	Educate	Information		Information	All we have to do is tell them the numbers	
Manipulation	Inform		Passive participation	Manipulation	All we have to do is get the numbers right	

Figure 1: typologies of participation (Green and Hunton-Clarke, 2003)

1.3 Analysing stakeholders

The degree of stakeholder involvement along the process might vary for different stakeholders. This mainly depends on the actual influence/importance this stakeholder has on the successful development and sustainability of the future network, or the extent to which stakeholders might be affected by the project or the network. So, a first step to take is to gain an understanding of 'who are the stakeholders' and 'what are their perceived stakes', often referred to as stakeholder analysis. Stakeholder analysis can be described here as the process to i) identify individuals, groups and organisations who are affected by or can affect the success of a future network of LLs and RIs and to ii) prioritise these individuals and groups for involvement throughout the development process (stakeholder mapping).

For the first step, identification of stakeholders, several approaches are used, such as focus groups, semi-structured interviews, snow-ball sampling, using expert opinion. Quite often, a combination of these is used, as identifying stakeholders is usually an iterative process. Additional stakeholders are added when the process evolves. Because of many practical reasons, it is not possible to include all stakeholders that are desired or identified. This topic is addressed in 1.4 challenges in stakeholder engagement.

In a second step, prioritisation in 'who to involve when' will be necessary, especially as we are working in a European-wide context. Several criteria and methods can be used to further categorise and prioritise stakeholders to be engaged along the process. These methods are often referred to as 'stakeholder mapping'. According to Reed et al. (2009), methods to characterise and classify stakeholders tend to follow two broad approaches: i) top-down "analytical categorisations" and; ii) bottom-up "reconstructive methods". Analytical categorisations are based on a top-down classification, usually by structuring stakeholders by using matrices or Venn diagrams. Criteria to classifying then along the different dimensions of the matrices might vary. A first example includes the classification along dimensions of interest and influence. A well-known method is the power interest matrix, by using a two dimensional grid. The first dimension categorises stakeholders by interest or stake and the second dimension is in terms of power. Along these dimensions, Eden and Ackermann (2011), distinguish between 4 categories of stakeholders based on their interest and influence in the future network: "Players", "Context setters", "Subjects" and "Crowd".

- **Players** are stakeholders who should be actively groomed, because they have high interest in and influence over a particular phenomenon.
- **Context setters** are highly influential, but have little interest. Because of this, they may be a significant risk, and should be monitored and managed.
- **Subjects** have high interest but low influence and although by definition they are supportive, they lack the capacity for impact, although they may become influential by forming alliances with other stakeholders. These are often the marginal stakeholders that development projects seek to empower.
- **The "Crowd"** are stakeholders who have little interest in or influence over desired outcomes and there is little need to consider them in much detail or to engage with them.

Figure 2: Classifying stakeholders along the dimensions of interest and power (Eden and Ackermann, 2011)

A second example of dimensions for classification is supportive and unresponsive. Here, 5 different categories can be distinguished:

- **Unaware:** they are not aware of the project and its potential impacts on them
- **Resistant:** they are aware of the project but not in support of it
- **Neutral:** They are aware of the project but have no opinion regarding their support for it
- **Supportive:** they are supportive of the project and wish it to succeed
- **Leading:** they are actively engaged in project success and willing to lend assistance to help it succeed.

Besides these analytical categorisations, there are also more bottom-up approaches, in which the parameters for classification are defined by the stakeholders themselves. This means that stakeholders are already involved also for this first step in the stakeholder management process (Reed et al., 2009). More and more literature also emphasises the importance of considering the dynamic nature of stakeholder engagement, as interest and influence might change over time. By taking this into account, the impact of such change can be considered. Within our project, we can think of potential funders of the future partnerships that become more visible over the years, changing institutions in particular organisations of interest, etc.

1.4 Stakeholder engagement: challenges

1.4.1 Alignment with other ongoing initiatives

Developing a framework for a future network of LLs and RIs, as the overall objective of ALL-Ready, is one of the goals of a wider, future partnership on AE. This partnership has been proposed by the EC as a collaboration model between the EC and the Member States in order

to foster the transition of European farming and food systems towards AE [1]. This partnership will be funded under the Horizon Europe work programme and scheduled to start in 2023-24. In the preparation of the partnership, the EC also relied from the early stage of development on a bottom-up approach. The EC has been taking a proactive role by ensuring participation of relevant stakeholders which includes consultations with Member States authorities, network of European regions, ERA-NETs, technological platforms, etc., and through the organisation of participatory discussions (workshops, webinars, etc.). Furthermore, the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) has established a new strategic working group on AE (SWG-AE), that is responsible for developing the partnership proposal, in close coordination with Member States and Associated countries and other stakeholders. Finally, besides ALL-Ready, another CSA has been funded, Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU), to co-develop the framework for the future network. The stakeholders that have an interest in each of these initiatives, and thus might be engaged along the road, are largely identical. However, their interest or stake might be different for multiple ongoing initiatives. It is therefore important to make stakeholders aware of these simultaneous initiatives, so that they also continue to see the bigger picture and complementarity. In this way, they can judge for themselves for which initiative they want to/can commit themselves and at which level. To stay aware of other initiatives, project partners of ALL-Ready participate in the SCAR task forces to assure timeline alignments, and organise bilateral discussions with the other CSA on a regular basis. Besides this, there is ongoing communication and consultation with the EC. The number of stakeholders that have an interest, or a stake, in the network and the partnership, is very large. By identifying stakeholders as much as possible within ALL-Ready consortium network, we try to avoid addressing the same stakeholders over and over again, and as such over-involvement and stakeholder fatigue by seeking complementarity by those involved in the other ongoing initiatives. This challenge might also come as an opportunity, as it is not possible to include all stakeholders along the way. By collaborating with other ongoing initiatives, we can make agreements on who involves which stakeholders, and for what purpose. For example, for mapping initiatives across Europe, we will focus not on the whole of Europe, but on a set of countries. The other countries will be included by the other CSA funded, AE4EU.

1.4.2 Identification of stakeholders: an iterative process

The transition process entails a considerable number of stakeholders, at both European, national and local level/regional level. Identifying all stakeholders who might be affected is challenging, due to the multi- and transdisciplinary nature of stakeholders involved in fostering agroecological transition and due to the large geographical scale. Target groups will initially be identified by consulting consortium partners and their networks. We will assure including representatives of relevant ongoing related large-scale initiatives, such as FACCE-JPI, ERA-NETs, Core Organic, research organisations coordinating H2020 projects, the European Joint programme EJP SOIL, etc. By snowball sampling and an iterative approach, we want to enlarge our network throughout the project lifetime, by ongoing identification of stakeholder groups and networks.

1.4.3 Organising stakeholder engagement activities: online or in person?

Stakeholder engagement implies a rather demanding commitment on stakeholders. Although engagement offers particular gains or opportunities for networking, these people who ordinarily have rather busy working lives, should take some time off from their normal duties to engage in this process. It is appropriate to spend this time as efficiently as possible through a considered alternation between online and in person meetings. Remote working saves both time and money. It additionally allows reaching more people because the threshold

¹ [European R&I partnership on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/european-r-i-partnership-on-agroecology-living-labs-and-research-infrastructures)

for participation is lower. Yet there are also disadvantages. In order to keep stakeholders involved in the long term and to create ownership, it is important to assure a higher level of stakeholder engagement. Informal moments are very important to create trust, confidence and reinforce connections. Moreover, more creative forms of participatory methods can be used during 'in person' meetings. Therefore, a good balance between online and in person activities is desired. The consideration will mainly take into account the level of engagement we want to create for particular stakeholder groups (inform, consult, collaborate) just as the objective of the activity. Therefore, the project also includes funds to reimburse travel expenses of stakeholders.

1.4.4 Speaking the same language

Engaging stakeholders at European, national and local level also includes challenges regarding use of language. Especially at the local level, it is not self-evident to expect stakeholders to have a good command of English. This will be taken into account by organising regional workshops and conducting interviews in the local language. In this way, we want to avoid that opinions and knowledge of people who are less familiar with English are not accounted for. In addition, we need to be vigilant in the use of concepts such as AE, LLs, RIs, etc. Even if the stakeholders are familiar with them, the ambiguity of these concepts allows for different interpretations. It is important to take this sufficiently into account. In WP1 an effort was already made to come to a detailed description of these concepts to create common understanding (D1.1: Mambrini-Doudet et al., 2021). Nevertheless, additional effort is needed to adapt our language to the stakeholder groups that will be approached. The vocabulary that is used at the European level needs to be translated if discussion with local stakeholders is aspired. Surveys and interviews need to be tested with these stakeholders before being sent out to ensure that they are sufficiently clear and not misunderstood.

1.4.5 Stakeholder engagement at European level: how to take into account diversity?

Furthermore, the establishment of a network of RIs and LLs at European level covers a large area, characterised by a very large group of potential stakeholders. Due to the diversity of geographical (and thus cultural and socio-economic) contexts within Europe, the needs and challenges of farming systems across regions might vary substantially. In order to take this diversity into account as much as possible, geographical representativeness will be an important criterion when setting up activities (e.g. mapping, set up of pilot network, etc). The involvement of stakeholders representing organisations at the European, national and local levels will be guaranteed. When identifying key stakeholder groups, we will therefore take these criteria into account in order to be sufficiently representative at multiple levels. Furthermore, several efforts will be made to identify the needs at local, national and European level. This allows us to better communicate and address added value across Member States. Assuring and communicating added value is particularly important in the early stages, to ensure that requirements are met, and long term engagement will be achieved.

1.4.6 How to involve the 'hard to reach' stakeholders?

Because of many practical reasons important stakeholders cannot be reached. The stakeholders most easy to reach are the ones in the networks of the project partners. Not all stakeholders have access to internet, aren't part of an easy to reach network or aren't part of a network, have a lack of trust in EU related/organised processes, have a lack of time, don't see the added value of participating in a EU wide network.

So, stakeholders that can be reached might have different opinions than those who can't be reached. That can cause a bias in the results of engaging with stakeholder. Developing the process with the easy to reach might not take into account the problems, wishes and values of the hard to reach stakeholders, making them feeling even more excluded from the future network that is aimed to set up.

2. Development of stakeholder engagement plan

Various groups of stakeholders were involved in all work packages (WP) of the ALL-Ready project, depending on the particular objectives of each of the WPs. It is therefore important that stakeholder engagement took place in a well-coordinated manner throughout the whole project, using the most adequate participatory methods for different levels of participation. In what follows, we will provide an overview of the most important steps of developing a stakeholder engagement plan for the ALL-Ready project: Identification of stakeholder groups, stakeholder mapping and planning stakeholder engagement.

2.1 Identification of important stakeholder groups

Identifying stakeholder groups to engage in the ALL-Ready project was an iterative process (see 1.1 *Stakeholder engagement as a key prerequisite in co-creation processes*). In the first year of the ALL-Ready project, several complementary methods were used:

- Exploration of the preparatory documents of the partnership “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” (AGROECOLOGY partnership) just as the project proposal were used to identify important groups of stakeholders: documents of SCAR-AE, documents of DG AGRI²,
- A set of interviews with WP leads of the ALL-Ready consortium, aiming to identify stakeholders related to the objectives of each of the WPs
- Snowball sampling: the workshops that were already organised in the frame of the ALL-Ready project that brings information from stakeholders about unknown stakeholders
- The SCAR Taskforces documents and meetings
- Partners and networks of relevant projects such as AE4EU, ROADMAP, UNISECO, DIVERIMPACTS.

However, in the following years of the ALL-Ready project, as more actors were involved and participated in the planned workshops and/or other interventions (interviews, events), more stakeholders were identified (snowball effect). The continuous collaboration with the SCAR AE group and the other CSA Agroecology4Europe automatically led to the identification of more stakeholders.

2.2 Stakeholder mapping

Because of the amount of data about stakeholders gathered in the identifying phase 2.1 there was a need for a framework meaningful for the ALL-Ready process in order to structure this stakeholders and stakeholder groups. The proposed structuring framework or stakeholder map takes into account **four different criteria**: Geographical scale; Type of stakeholder group; Potential interest of the stakeholder in the future network of LLs and RIs; Importance of the stakeholder for the future network of LLs and RIs. The criteria “Geographical scale”

² [aellri-ec-input-partnership-discussion.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

and “Stakeholder groups” were indicated in several interviews and WP1 workshops as important. The other two criteria are mentioned as important criteria in stakeholder analysis.

1) **“Geographical scale”** refers to the scale level at which the stakeholder mainly operates.

Three scale levels were distinguished:

- **EU level:** This level includes the EC, SCAR-AE, researchers involved in projects funded by EU research programmes (H2020), LLs and RIs with an EU-wide scope and activities, EU wide networks related to AE potentially influencing funding, governance and running of the network. Very specific examples include FACCE-JPI, and the ERA-NETs SusCrop, SusAN, IPM, Core Organic, Biodiversa, the PRIMA initiative, the BIOEAST initiative on Bioeconomy, the European Joint Programme EJP SOIL, as well as activities of the EIP-AGRI.
- **National level:** This level includes national ministries, authorities and funding bodies, national operating NGO’s, farmers and other agro-food sectors unions, national operating consumers union/networks, LLs and RIs with a national scope and activities, potential private funders and foundations. To form a bridge between the European and national level, the ALL-Ready consortium had close contact with national contact points (NCP) in the different member states. These national contact points can be linked to national authorities, extension or research. These persons are supposed to disseminate outputs of the project to relevant stakeholders in the Member State they represent. They are key in informing relevant stakeholders, LL, and RI in their member state about the AGROECOLOGY partnership, engage them, as well as encourage them to participate in surveys that were disseminated in the course of the project.
- **Regional and local level:** This level includes regional authorities, municipalities, regional based NGO’s, farmers and agro-food actors. To involve the local level at a regular basis throughout the project, a pilot network of LLs and RIs has been established. This pilot network contains 16 members identified within the 13 partner countries. The pilot network served as a small-scale testbed to experiment and give feedback on the tools and recommendations developed in the ALL-Ready project and to build cooperation and prepare joint activities between the different AE-focused LLs, RIs and open innovation arrangements (OIA) across Europe. The pilot network was brought together during yearly workshops. This level included stakeholder groups not directly involved in the future network but indirectly involved by influencing the transition to AE and/or by being influenced by the transition to AE.

The three distinguished scale levels are not strictly separated. Individuals can take up different roles at different scale levels. They might be involved in local initiatives while at the same time operating in EU wide projects. The future network of LLs and RIs is also meant to connect the scale levels.

2) Types of stakeholder groups

At each level we have similar types of stakeholder groups. A stakeholder group is a group of stakeholders that operates more or less in the same “domain of action”. Although there is not a strict definition for “domain”, it can be interpreted as a particular activity or interest: research, policy, farm advisory, food value chain, citizen movement

Farmers
Researchers
Policy makers
Agricultural educators
Farm advisors

Value chain actors
Citizen movements
NGO's (environmental, social justice)
...

Overlap between the domains is possible. LLs can be understood as stakeholder groups that combine one or more of the indicated domains.

3) What's in it for them (interest)?

To engage with stakeholders for developing the future network, it is important to indicate what their interest in the network is, i.e. what's in it for them if they would participate in or collaborate with the future network. If there wouldn't be an added value in participating, it will be impossible to involve them on a long-term basis.

4) What is the importance of the stakeholder for development of the future network of LLs and RIs

Another dimension that has to be taken into account is how important a stakeholder is for this future network of LLs and RIs for achieving the objectives of the network. LLs and RIs or similar Open Innovation Arrangements that are committed to AE transition are the core of the future network and thus important stakeholders. LLs are considered as stakeholders as such but also as open innovation networks based on multi-stakeholder arrangements, with at the center the farmers as end-users. Representatives of LL will be engaged in this process, and expected to represent to some extent the interests of its network members. It is also clear that funding will be necessary for financing the activities of the future network. In this regard, potential funders, among which national ministries, are important stakeholders with a major influence on developing the future network.

2.3 Mapping stakeholders in the ALL-Ready project

Stakeholder group @EU level	What's in it for them? (interest)	Importance for the network of LLs and RIs
SCAR AE working group	text for supporting the document of the AGROECOLOGY partnership	See text box
EAB	Cooperation and networking for future activities	See text box
Research	<p>It would provide scientists with a network of close to the ground research sites that would deliver harmonised data with a long-term perspective also with local specificities.</p> <p>Improved understanding of AE, LLs and RIs that can help to set future research targets.</p> <p>Build a solid evidence and scientific knowledge base on how AE LLs and RIs can contribute to find locally diverse solutions to mitigate the effects of climate change.</p> <p>Funding opportunities</p> <p>Cooperation and networking for future projects</p>	Transdisciplinary EU wide research input
European Commission	<p>To meet Green Deal objectives</p> <p>It will provide for a more strategic approach in the longer-term along with a broader coverage of the EU territory.</p>	<p>Funding, other support, support for potential policy change</p> <p>the European Commission which bodies will have a leading role in developing and implementing the SRIA and will be responsible for its outputs</p>
Value chain actors	<p>Funding opportunities</p> <p>Cooperation and networking for future projects</p>	Wide network in agro-food chain
NGO's	Cooperation and networking for future projects	Funding, EU wide network support

Farmers' unions	Diverse pool of hands-on AE practices and approaches that they can readily use in their locality to transition to agroecological practices. Funding opportunities Cooperation and networking for future projects	Wide support and EU wide network
AE related networks	increased awareness about future funding opportunities	EU wide network support
AKIS	improved understanding about AE and transdisciplinary methods	dissemination of AE methods and tools
Stakeholder group @national level	What's in it for them? (interest)	Importance for the network of LLs and RIs
Research	It would provide scientists with a network of close to the ground research sites that would deliver harmonised data with a long-term perspective.	Provide national research data
Policy makers	It can provide them input about actual barriers in education, advisory services, national regulations in order to remove them.	Provide national legislative frame
Value chain actors	They can discover new possibilities of adding value to AE products.	Provide input of experiences, promote network
NGO's	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide input of experiences, promote network
Farm advisors	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide input of experiences, promote network to provide the whole range of knowledge and practices which are necessary for a transition towards AE of a substantial part of the EU farming sector.
Education institutes	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide input of experiences, promote network

Farmers and Farmers' unions	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Promote the network
Consumer associations	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Promote the network
AE related networks	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide input of experiences, promote network
Stakeholder group @local/regional level	What's in it for them? (interest)	Importance for the Network of LLs and RIs
Researchers	It would provide scientists with a network of close to the ground research sites that would deliver harmonised data with a long-term perspective.	Provide local/regional research data
Policy makers	It can provide them input about actual and local barriers in education, advisory services, regional regulations in order to remove them where possible	Provide local/regional legislative framework, legislative problems
Value chain actors	They can discover new possibilities of adding value to AE products in local chains.	Provide local/ regional AE practices, experiences
NGO's	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide local/ regional AE practices, experiences and problems
Farm advisors	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	Provide local/ regional AE practices, experiences and problems
Education institutes	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	
Farmers and farmers' unions	It would benefit producers by creating spaces in which they can experiment and test their own solutions for more sustainable practices, learn from peers and get the support of scientists. Working on groups of farms would also be supported. European farmers are key to manage the transition to sustainability and one of the objectives of the Farm to Fork Strategy, which is also fully in line	Provide local/ regional AE practices, experiences

	with the general objective of this partnership, is to strengthen their efforts to tackle climate change, protect the environment and preserve biodiversity.	
Representatives of LLs	It is a possibility to cooperate with LLs and RIs in an international context.	They can become partner in the network
Citizens movements	It provides opportunities to contribute to reducing the environmental impact of agriculture and its contribution to healthier and more sustainable diets, and by offering possibilities for regional businesses and citizens' involvement in experimentations, thus helping connect consumers with producers and foster access to agroecological products.	They can provide local support for the AE transition in general

Table 1: stakeholder groups organised in a structured framework along the dimensions of interest, importance, geographical representation and domain of action³

³ The information in this table is based on the output from regional workshops (WP4), interviews with network representatives and NCP's and on activities with pilot network members.

2.4 Planning Stakeholder engagement

The overall objective of the stakeholder engagement plan was to provide an overview of who to involve when and how. On the one hand this stakeholder engagement plan was closely motivated by the objectives of the different WPs of the project. On the other hand when elaborating the activities planned in each WP, new insights came in which provided new focusses on the engagement of stakeholders, i.e. some stakeholder groups seem to be more important than other stakeholder groups, a stakeholder group was under the radar or a stakeholder group was very hard to reach in the foreseen amount of time of the project. In what follows, we first provide an overview of the WPs, including a description of objectives, what is expected from stakeholder engagement and how it evolved during the elaboration of the WP/project activities. Then, we will provide an overview of who was engaged in each of the WPs and the level of engagement needed to meet WP objectives.

2.4.1 Objectives structured along WPs

WP1: Vision and mission of the network

A first objective of this WP is to describe key concepts related to the 'transition to AE', just as describing the potential of LLs and RIs to accelerate this transition. A second objective is the identification of inclusion criteria to determine which types of organisations will constitute the network. A third objective is to develop a vision and a mission for the future network. Stakeholders to be engaged need to have knowledge on values, competencies, policies and activities needed for agroecological transition both at the European as the more local level. This WP mainly engaged stakeholders operating at European level. However, the inclusion criteria as output of this WP, were used to develop a survey that was used in WP2 to map LL, RIs and other OIAs at the local level.

WP2: Mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms for doing participatory research and innovation on AE

A first objective of this WP is to map existing LLs, RIs and other OIAs across Europe. A second objective is to get more insights into barriers and incentives for innovation arrangements supporting AE transition. These include societal drivers, particularly funding arrangements and regulatory frameworks, both at European and more regional level. A final objective is to identify a common set of key performance indicators for a European network of AE LLs. Key stakeholders to include are National Contact Points (NCPs) which include both representatives of ministries, research and the farming community with a clear view on existing initiatives supporting agroecological transitions, just as funding schemes and regulatory frameworks influencing this transition. Because of the very broad scope of the mapping task, several methods are used to reach as many stakeholders as possible: interviews with NCPs, regional workshops with representatives of LLs, RIs an OIAs, and finally the online survey based on inclusion criteria developed in WP1.

WP3: Stakeholder engagement

In this WP, one of the objectives is to design and align the process of stakeholder engagement and co-creation throughout the project. Stakeholders to be included are the WP leads and

consortium members just as representatives of other ongoing initiatives to align stakeholder engagement activities and to address challenges of stakeholder engagement (see 1.2). The other objective is to establish and run a small-scale pilot network in order to test and give feedback on the tools and recommendations developed in the ALL-Ready project (across WPs), to build strong links and cooperation between the different AE-focused LLs, RIs and OIAs across Europe and to prepare joint activities in line with the common agroecological interest of the pilot members. Moreover, this WP also ensures that the findings of stakeholder engagement and the pilot network are properly synthesized in the form of stakeholder recommendations. Key stakeholders to be included are the member LLs and RIs of the pilot network. These members will be selected based on consultation of the ALL-Ready partners. However, throughout the project, especially by the online survey of WP1, new initiatives will be identified. Based on selection criteria some of them will be selected and invited to join the pilot network. Other stakeholders may be indirectly national authorities and funding bodies that might ensure national support and complementary funding sources for the future network. Therefore, WP3 has to maintain a continuous and close collaboration across WP1-7, between the pilot members and between the pilot members and WP1-7.

WP4: Implementation and sustainability of the network

The overall aim of WP4 is to provide an implementation plan that ensures the added value and sustainability of the European network of LLs and RIs capturing and promoting long-term processes of agroecological transitions. The implementation plan will include a long-term funding strategy making use of complementarities and synergies of funding opportunities at EU, national and regional level to ensure the ambitions of the network in the long term. More specific objectives of WP4 are assessing key factors for the long-term sustainability of the network, identifying the added value and synergies of the network at European level, and co-constructing recommendations that inform the development of the implementation plan for the future network. The ambition is to engage with representatives of all stakeholder groups of agroecological transitions with potential interest in the future network to identify and utilise the added value of the network. The stakeholders of the pilot network will have a central role in co-developing recommendations for the long-term sustainability of the network, while potential funders of the future network and AGROECOLOGY partnership (public funders such as national ministries, private funders, small scale funders) are key stakeholders for the development of the funding strategy of the implementation plan. The representatives of the AE LLs, RIs and OIAs that were identified via the mapping exercises of WP2 will be consulted via semi-structured interviews. In a later stage they will be involved twice in two series of four consecutive regional workshops in the four regions of the EU to mobilise LLs, RIs and OIAs for the AGROECOLOGY partnership. Finally representatives of agro-food networks of networks are to be invited for semi-structured interviews to gather recommendations for the long-term sustainability of the network.

WP5: capacity building

The overall objective of WP5 is to scope, test and implement a capacity building program (CBP) that serves identified key end-users and their needs (Subtask 5.1.2) by the specification of the skills, competencies and knowledge needed (Subtask 5.1.1) to run a European wide network of LLs and RIs, but also for AE transition in general, for managing a shared RI and/or LL and for taking part in co-design and experimental processes. The active participation of the identified key stakeholders below is crucial to guarantee the developed CBP is in line with their needs. Therefore, they will be asked to actively co-design the CBP during the test phase. Key stakeholders are the potential end users of CBP, which in first place are the members of the future network of LLs and RIs, thus representatives of LLs and RIs. Next to them the CBP will serve AE researchers, policy makers, farmers, citizens (consumers, civil society organisations, NGOs...), intermediaries (advisors, LL managers...) and other value

chain actors (traders, retailers...). Other stakeholders to include are representatives of the AKIS in each of the member states to have a clear understanding of existing capacity building initiatives to support agroecological transition. While implementing the activities of the WP, it became clear that in order to organise a good and feasible CBP, there is need for a clear focus on certain stakeholder groups. It was decided that LLs, RIs and OIAs were the main stakeholders for co-designing a CBP as they are considered as the key end-users of the CBP. While for the stakeholder groups at the European level and at the local level recommendations will be formulated to organise further capacity building. For formulating the recommendations at the local level the same local and regional representatives of the AE LLs, RIs and OIAs in the above described regional workshops (WP4) are to be consulted. The representatives of the agro-food networks of networks will be questioned about what could be recommended concerning capacity building on the European level.

WP6: knowledge and data management

Agroecology research and innovation network scaling up from local to the global one is a complex process. Complexity relates to stakeholders, functioning and service delivering. Meeting these complexities is also a major driver on the data and knowledge management perspectives, which require important efforts on the harmonisation, integration and interoperability, taking into account the connectivity with the rest of WPs in terms of drivers and variables considered. In order to achieve this main aim, a proper demonstrator given in the form of a Virtual Research Environment, integrating and providing Blockchain-based technology and other e-Services will be developed, together with the proper DMP and other innovative tools. Key stakeholders are the members of the LLs, RIs from the pilot network that are interested and engaged in data sharing and management.

WP7: Communication and dissemination

The objectives of this WP are to communicate and disseminate project activities and outcomes to different target groups. This is described in the communication plan (D7.1: Haller et al., 2021). Stakeholders to reach are both those who might benefit from the future network, just as those who might impact the development, governance and long term sustainability of the future network.

2.4.2 HOW to engage stakeholders?

2.4.2.1 Level of engagement

The four described dimensions for structuring stakeholder groups to be engaged, together with the objectives of the WPs, informs us about the level of participation needed for each of the different stakeholder groups throughout the project. Table 2 provides an overview of the different levels of participation for each of the stakeholder groups for each of the WPs. This table has been co-created with WP leads of the project.

The level of participation defines to a great extent the methods to be used in the stakeholder engagement process of the ALL-Ready project:

Informing the stakeholder: informing the stakeholders is organised to a large extent via the website, newsletter, social media channels, direct email exchanges and other actions formulated in the communication plan (D7.1: Haller et al., 2021)

Consulting the stakeholder: consultations take place mainly by the use of surveys (pilot network, mapping in WP2) and interviews

Involving the stakeholder: workshops are organised to work directly with the stakeholders to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the outputs generated by the ALL-Ready project partners in the work packages

Collaborating with the stakeholders: co-creative workshops (experimenting and testing), bilateral meetings and discussions (live and online) in small groups are set up to find solutions together in preparing the future network

2.4.2.2 Special stakeholder groups in ALL-Ready

The **External Advisory Board (EAB)** consist of about 20 European or international organisations or initiatives, themselves often representing a great number of other (national/regional) stakeholder organisations active in the environment or agricultural sectors (see Appendix for more detailed list of members). Besides providing advice on the project's workplan, activities and strategic documents, EAB involvement will ensure and maximise the flow of information to and from the consortium so as to take advantage of the knowledge produced by other already existing initiatives as well as ensures that new ideas and emerging initiatives are duly considered. We can rely on them to help identify relevant stakeholders just as supporting their engagement.

The **SCAR Strategic Working Group (SWG) on Agroecology (SCAR-EU)** consists of a group of ministries (or other organisations such as research councils) from 9 MS/AC, with the overall objective to support research policy development for AE at national, EU and international level. It is platform for Member States and Associated Countries to share views, create common visions together with the European Commission (EC) with a unified voice on AE and AE LL-related research and innovation needs and how to integrate it into national and European research programmes. More specifically, regarding development of the AGROECOLOGY partnership, this working group will centralise and integrate the efforts for the process of preparing the partnership. They aim at writing the "Partnership proposal" , which will be the basis of the Partnership call that will be included in the Work Programme 2023-2024. For this endeavor, they will rely on the efforts and expertise of ALL-READY. Coordination and timeline alignments will be achieved by participation of ALL-READY members in the different task forces of the working group just as participation of members of the SCAR-AE working group during activities organised within ALL-READY. When needed, bilateral meetings will be organised on specific topics.

One of the aims of ALL-Ready project is to launch and run **a pilot network** including AE LLs, research infrastructure or other open innovation arrangements from Europe in frame of WP3. The pilot network contains 17 members within the 13 partner countries plus 2 external advisor LLs from Canada and Spain. The pilot network served as a small-scale testbed to experiment and give feedback on the tools and recommendations developed in the ALL-Ready project and to build cooperation and prepare joint activities between the different AE-focused LLs, RIs and OIAs across Europe. The members of the pilot network can identify further local and national stakeholders as well.

National Contact Points

National contact points are people knowledgeable about national AE 'landscapes' in terms of research, practice, funding, innovation and policies. To get as many perspectives, and snowballing avenues as possible, we have identified this list of NCP among national authorities, extension and researchers within this rather broad field. Furthermore, these national contact points can also act as entry points to other resource persons.

Stakeholder group @EU level	Appropriate level of participation					
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
SCAR AE working group	Inform/collaborate		Inform	Inform / consult / collaborate	Involve	Inform
AE4EU	Collaborate		Involve	Collaborate	Involve	Collaborate
EAB	Involve		Involve	Consult / involve	Involve	Consult
Research	Inform, collaborate		Consult/involve	Consult / involve	Involve	
European Commission	Involve		Involve	Involve	Involve	
Value chain actors	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Involve	
NGO's	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
Farmers' unions	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
AE related networks	Involve		Consult	Consult / involve	Consult	
AKIS	Consult/collaborate		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
Stakeholder group @national level	Appropriate level of participation					
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6

Research	Consult	Consult	Consult/involve	Consult / collaborate	Involve
Policy makers/national authorities	Inform	Consult	Collaborate	Collaborate	Involve
Value chain actors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
NGO's	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
Farm advisors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
AKIS	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	consult
Farmers' unions	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Consult
Consumer associations	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	consult
Stakeholder group @local/regional level	Appropriate level of participation				
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5
Researchers	Inform		Involve	Inform / consult	Involve
Policy makers	Inform		Collaborate	Involve / collaborate	Involve
Value chain actors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
NGO's	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
Farm advisors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve

AKIS	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Consult
Farmers and farmers' unions	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
Representatives of LLs and RIs (pilot network)	Involve	Involve	Involve / collaborate	Collaborate Collaborate
Citizens movements	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve

Table 2: Level of participation for each of the stakeholder groups to meet objectives for each of the WP

2.4.3 WHEN to engage stakeholders?

The figure below gives an overview of the different events and methodologies used (workshops (WS), interviews, surveys, focus group, etc) for the different tasks structured within WPs according to the project's timeline. In the actual roll-out of the stakeholder engagement plan (see next chapter) there can be substantially deviated from this original time frame in function of a good alignment between WPs and with other ongoing initiatives.

	2021		2022		2023	
	jan-jun	jul-dec	jan-jun	jul-dec	jan-jun	jul-nov
WP1						
Key concepts: agroecology transition and role of LL and RI (D1.1)	WS					
Vision and mission of the future network + inclusion criteria (D1.3; D1.2)		WS				
WP2						
Mapping agroecology initiatives (D2.2; 2.4;2.5)	Regional WS including NCPs					
Mapping drivers and barriers for agroecology transition (D2.3)	Regional WS including NCPs					
Develop common set of KPI for the future network (D2.6)	Regional WS including NCPs					

WP3						
Needs and expectations of the pilot network (MS4)	Survey					
Pilot network co-creation activities (MS7)		Yearly WS (4-5 in total) and trimonthly online calls in-between WS				
Develop stakeholder recommendations for running future network (D3.3)						WS pilot network
WP4						
Added value of future network (D4.1)		Survey + WS				
Develop preconditions for sustainability (D4.2)			WS			
Implementation plan (D4.3)					Regional WS + final conference	
WP5						
Scoping capacity building by mapping the needs and key end users(D5.2)	Focus group, survey					
Prototyping the capacity building programme			WS			
Testing the capacity building programme (D5.3)					WS, Open LL Days	
WP6						
Co-develop a VRE (D6.4)	2 training WS					
Develop and test Data Management plan (D6.5)						

Table 3: overview of WPs, activities and timing for engaging stakeholders: version October 2021

3. Process of stakeholder engagement

Finally, we provide here a more detailed description of how stakeholders were involved in ALL-Ready, along the process of developing a framework for the European network of agroecological LLs and RIs. This includes aligning the involvement of stakeholders between the different tasks and WPs of ALL-Ready. Workshops or surveys were organized crossing multiple WPs because of reasons of logic and practical organisation (avoiding over-consulting stakeholders). Down here, we list the different events and project activities where we involved stakeholders. For each event, we describe how we involved the different stakeholders.

	2021		2022		2023	
	jan-jun	jul-dec	jan-jun	jul-dec	jan-jun	jul-nov
WP1						
Key concepts: agroecology transition and role of LL and RI (D1.1)	Workshop: towards a conceptual framework for agroecological transition (26.04.2021)					
Vision and mission of the future network + inclusion criteria (D1.3; D1.2)		Workshop: Towards a mission and vision for the future network of LLs and RIs (4.10.2021)				
WP2						
Framework for Mapping and analysis of agroecology and agroecology LLs and Ris (D2.1)	alignment between ALL-Ready and AE4EU mapping exercise (involve AE4EU)					
Mapping agroecology initiatives (D2.2; 2.4;2.5)		63 interviews with NCPs in 23 European countries	follow-up online survey send to LLs, Ris, OIAs identified during interviews with NCPs			

Mapping drivers and barriers for agroecology transition (D2.3)				4 Regional workshops to (i) mobilise LL actors in relation to AELLRI partnership and (ii) map initiatives (D.2.4 and D2.5).		
WP3						
Needs and expectations of the pilot network (MS4)	Survey for detecting members of the pilot network in 13 partner countries (May-June 2021)					
Pilot network co-creation activities (MS7)		First pilot network meeting (13-14.12.2021)		Second Pilot network meeting (4-5.07.2022) + Third Pilot network meeting (21-23.11.2022)		Fourth Pilot network meeting (14-16.06.2023)
Develop stakeholder recommendations for running future network (D3.3)				Workshop during Second Pilot network meeting: exercise on best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders (4-5.07.2022)		Workshop during Fourth Pilot network meeting: exercise on best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders
WP4						
Added value of future network (D4.1)			21 interviews (13 with selected LL, Ris and OIAs and 8 with selected funding organisations)	Second pilot network meeting (4-5.07.2022): validation of results		
Develop preconditions for sustainability (D4.2)				Interviews with other networks of networks + network analysis sessions at Third Pilot network meeting (21 - 23.11.2022) + regional workshops organised by WP2		

Implementation plan (D4.3)					Regional workshops (4) to review key elements of draft implementation plan and funding strategy	Session at pilot network workshop in July 2023 to co-design recommendations for final implementation plan and funding strategy
WPS						
Scoping capacity building by mapping the needs and key end users(D5.2; D5.1)		Workshop pilot network meeting: exploring competences, skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/Ris (13-14.12.2021); EAB meeting 4.10.2021	Survey for policy makers (Feb 2022): 59 respondents of 23 countries			
Prototyping the capacity building programme				Workshop 2nd pilot network meeting: What competencies and skills can a European network improve? (5.07.2022) Workshop third pilot network meeting: agreeing on + specifying the modules to develop in the CBP + training materials for the CBP database		
Testing and validating the capacity building programme (D5.3)						Testing final prototype session in the fourth pilot network meeting Validation workshop of CBP in the open living lab days in Barcelona (21-23.09.2023)

WP6						
Co-develop a VRE (D6.4)		Workshop pilot network: building the virtual lab (13-14.12.2021)		Workshop 2nd pilot network meeting: Functionalities of the Virtual lab (5.07.2022) Third pilot network meeting: training first version + evaluation of the tool (first version)		Fourth pilot network meeting: Training second version
WP7						
Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1)						
Science-policy dialogue (Task 7.2)		e.g GFRAS	e.g. meeting with FAO Agroecology Hub, workshop with OPTA	e.g. Biofach workshop, TP organics	e.g. International conference on agroecology	
Final conference						27.09.2023-Brussels
WP8						
EAB		4.10.2021				27.10.2023

Inform	
Consult	
Involve	
Collaborate	

Table 4: Overview of actual stakeholder engagement: WPs, activities and timing _ version October 2023

3.1 Workshop: Towards a conceptual framework for agroecology transition

- *Date/period in time*

26th April 2021, 14:00-16:00

- *Target audience*

Participants of this workshop were researchers and policy makers involved in agro-ecology transition, LLs and RIs, SCAR AE group. In total, 93 people participated.

- *Objectives*

This workshop was set up in the frame of WP1, coordinated by INRAE. The aim was to co-develop a conceptual framework to assess and record agroecological transition and the role of LLs and RIs within the transition. To do so, the objective of the workshop was to build and get feedback on the draft of a conceptual framework, developed by INRAE, which had been drawn from a literature review and two brainstorming sessions within the consortium. More concretely, the aim was to validate and refine the activities, the values, the competences and the policy incentives that characterise or are necessary for agroecology transition.

- *Approach*

The workshop was organised online, due to COVID-19 restrictions. After a short introduction on the ALL Ready project, objectives of the workshop and first draft of the framework, stakeholders were divided in 4 subgroups (break-out sessions) according to the 4 different themes: activities, values, competences and policy incentives characterising agroecological transition. Within each break-out sessions, participants were asked to add their ideas and suggestions to the first draft using MURAL as an interactive white board for exchange.

The break-out sessions were facilitated by EV ILVO, and each break out session was supported by at least 1 ALL-Ready colleague who is expert in the content. In this way, we guaranteed the monitoring of the virtual exchange on the different topics. After a short break, feedback was organised from each break-out sessions towards the plenary session and further steps were discussed.

A full report of the workshop can be found here: [ALL-Ready Workshop report - Conceptual Framework 26/04/2021 | Zenodo](#)

3.2 Workshop: Towards a mission & vision for the future network of LLs and RIs

- *Date/period in time*

4th October 2021, 10:00-13:00

- *Target audience*

Task force leaders of SCAR Agroecology and external advisory board members, involved in agroecology transition related networks. In total, 42 people participated.

- *Objectives*

The objective of the workshop was to build together with the stakeholders a (draft) mission and vision for the future network of LLs and RIs (WP1). We discussed the use of the developed (inclusion) criteria for LLs and RIs in the future network (WP1).

- *Approach*

To allow stakeholders to prepare for the workshop, preparatory documents were sent out: D1.1 and D1.2.

The workshop was organised online, due to COVID-19 restrictions. After a plenary short introduction, the participants were divided into 3 smaller groups/sessions, in order to enhance an in-depth discussion and to gain trust and confidence between participants. Mural was used as an interactive tool to enhance online collaboration and discussion.

First, stakeholders were asked to explore and gather ideas on the mission and vision of the network of LLs and RIs during interactive brainstorm sessions within the subgroups. The potential inclusion criteria and the online tool (=a questionnaire to get a better understanding of the criteria) were explained to all participants during a short plenary session. Following, stakeholders discussed the use of the criteria in the different break-out sessions. The workshop ended with a plenary feedback on the results and how this would be used in the further process.

3.3 Interviews: Mapping agroecological LLs and RIs in Europe

- *Date/period in time*

November - December 2021

- *Target audience*

The Respondents (or National Contact Points- NCPs) are the main entry point for providing an overview of the national contexts. These are professionals such as case officers in ministries, researchers, and civil society. Interviews were conducted with 63 interviewees, representing policymaking, research and practice were identified and have consented to be interviewed for each of the 23 countries to be mapped.

- *Objectives*

This activity was set up in the frame of WP2, coordinated by Aarhus University and INRAE. The main objective was to map and analyse RIs, LLs and open innovation arrangements, along with policies and funding arrangements across Europe, that are linked to agroecology transition. This is with the ambition to gain an overview of the 'landscape' and understand enablers, barriers and incentives for innovation for agroecological transition, with specific attention to:

- The innovation systems that underpin AE systems, such as AE LLs and research

- The role of societal drivers, in particular funding arrangements and regulatory frameworks

- *Approach*

An interview guide was designed on the basis of the characterisations and definitions of what constitutes agroecological production systems and agroecological LLs and RIs, prepared in WP1. The interview guide contained (1) a series of closed questions as well as (2) a series of in-depth open-ended questions. The closed questions allowed for some degree of comparison across countries. The open questions allowed for elaboration of responses to the closed questions and for additional reflections. Questions are organised thematically, with closed questions being followed by open ones.

3.4 Survey to set up the pilot network

- *Date/period in time*

Between 17 May-18 June 2021

- *Target audience*

LLs and RIs known by the project partners

- *Objectives*

This survey was developed in the frame of WP3, coordinated by ÖMKi

(1) to map/identify already existing AE LLs, RIs and OIAs within the partner countries;

(2) to select forerunner members from the submitted initiatives based on a selection criterion in order to launch the pilot network and

(3) to collect the needs and expectations of the submitted initiatives with regards to the pilot network.

- *Approach*

Inputs were gathered from the candidate LLs and RIs between 17 May-18 June 2021 in form of the pilot network selection survey (see MS4: Needs and expectations for the pilot network defined). 16 forerunner pilot members were selected (9 LL, 5 RI, 2 LL+RI), in addition 2 external advisors (1 LL, 1 LL+RI) will support the work of pilot network. The needs and expectations of the pilot were separately analysed and clustered into seven expectations and seven needs based on similar opinions and responses by the candidate members which is documented in *Milestone 4 - Needs and expectations for pilot network defined*.

3.5 Kick-off pilot network

- *Date/period in time*

13-14 December 2021

- *Target audience*

Representatives of LLs and RIs from the pilot network. In total, 33 people participated. This included project partners as well.

- *Objectives*

The overall objective of the meeting was **to launch the ALL-Ready pilot network** (WP3) which has been prepared since July 2021. To reach this aim, specific objectives were also pursued:

- (1) Make members familiar with the project through introductory presentations about ALL-Ready, the aims of the pilot network and the AGROECOLOGY partnership,
- (2) to get the members to know each other and initiate cooperation through the pilot member presentations and the match-making workshop,
- (3) to present and ask feedback from the members on already developed concepts of the project such as the inclusion criteria, vision and mission for the future network or the use of the online selection tool and
- (4) to contribute to the ongoing work of different WPs with members' expertise through the five workshops.

- *Approach*

The following methods were used:

Validation session: this method engaged participants to work with and discuss a predefined set of topics, ideas in order to spark debate and arrive to a common understanding or set of preferences.

This method was applied only during the joint network activities workshop (related to WP3). In case of the pilot network, the predefined set of ideas were presented in relation to the expectations and needs of the pilot network, individual agroecological interests and activities and the framework for agroecological transition.

Mapping: this method involved collecting information verbally or through writing from participants on a given topic area of interest, and then recording it on an online workboard or some type of 'map' that the group can logically and visually follow and constantly can give feedback. This primary method that was used by the workshop sessions was dedicated to WP3-5-6 .

Match-making: this method helped to identify and connect (match) members, initiatives (LL/RIs) with common agroecological interests, activities, expertise, experiences, strengths which results in creating collaborative connections, themes, linkages and realising opportunities that mutually benefit both parties. This method was applied only during the joint network activities workshop (related to WP3).

3.6 External Advisory board meetings

- *Date/period in time*

4/10/2021 and 27/09/2023

- *Target audience*

EAB members

- *Objectives*

The first EAB meeting was organised to present the achievements of the project so far and to ask for feedback and recommendations for the further development of the project. The second meeting was organised at the very end of the project, so the focus was on presenting and gaining feedback on the main results from the project.

- *Approach*

The first EAB meeting was an online with the EAB members and the WP leads. The achievements of each WP were presented via powerpoint and oral feedback was gathered. The second EAB meeting was organised as an in person meeting in Brussels. The achievements of each WP were presented via powerpoint and feedback was gathered.

3.7 Survey for mapping LLs and RIs

- *Date/period in time*

March – April 2022

- *Target audience*

This survey was developed by WP1 and WP2 partners, coordinated by INRAE and Aarhus University respectively. The survey was sent out to representatives of LLs, RIs and OIAs across Europe that were mapped in the interviews with the NCPs.

- *Objectives*

To identify activities, values and funding sources of LLs and RIs in AE transition. To have a basis for selection of LLs and RIs to interview for gathering more in-depth information in WP4 (see 3.9 interviews WP4).

3.8 Survey to assess needs for capacity building

- *Date/period in time*

February 2022

- *Target audience*

NCP's that are policy makers and decision makers, related to the field of Agriculture of Member States, Associated countries (Bosnia & Herzegovina, Iceland, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, Israel and Turkey) and Countries in process to association (UK, Albania, Kosovo)

- *Objectives*

The survey was developed by WP5 coordinator, ENOLL. The survey was developed to get feedback from policy makers and decision makers across EU about proposed (the scoped) capacity building topics and formats.

- *Approach*

In a short survey, participants were asked about their perspective on the scoped capacity building items, and they were asked to prioritise their most important item from the proposed list of capacity building items. The survey was hosted via Surveylegend and included all necessary privacy measurements to guarantee the privacy of all participants. In total over 200 policy makers and/or decision makers received an invitation to participate in the survey and 59 people from 23 countries (Albania, Austria, Belgium, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Luxemburg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Slovenia, United Kingdom, Turkey) started the survey.

3.9 Interviews with LLs, RIs to assess added value of the future network

- *Date/period in time*

April-June 2022

- *Target audience*

Selected LLs, RIs and OIAs in Europe (identified in WP2 via interviews with NCPs and via an online questionnaire).

- *Objectives*

The interviews were carried out on the one hand to collect more in-depth information about challenges, needs and expectations from the agroecological community for the future network of AE LLs and RIs. On the other hand, they aim at identifying the needs and expectations of funding agencies concerning the future network. The interviews were done in the frame of WP4, more specifically for identifying the added value of the future network.

- *Approach*

Semi-structured interviews were carried out via phone or via online communication tools.

3.10 Second pilot network meeting

- *Date/period in time*

4-5 July 2022, Ghent (Belgium)

- *Target audience*

Representatives of the members of the pilot network. In total, 21 people participated, a combination of project partners and pilot network members.

- *Objectives*

In the pilot network meeting the different objectives of the different WPs were addressed. From the perspective of WP3 the pilot network the aims were fourfold:

- to operationalise the collaborative themes of the pilot network by agreeing what activities/tasks are feasible to do by the end of September 2023 and to assign members to realise the tasks,
- to arrive to a priority list of tasks,
- identify agroecological research needs of the members,
- to identify gaps in current membership, what characteristics we are lacking and who should be involved as members in the network (during the next wave of applications).

From the perspective of WP4 the session aims were to (1) update and reflect with pilot network members on the main results of the interviews on the added value of the network and (2) to inform pilot network members on the next steps and their envisaged forthcoming involvement.

The overall objective of WP5 is to prepare and initiate a CBP for the future network of LL and RI supporting AE transition. Rolling out the CBP will support the transition of European agri-food systems to AE by promoting AE and LL approaches.

The objectives of the session were twofold:

- to present the main 'needs for capacity building' that we identified during the first phase (scoping of the capacity building plan),
- to co-decide with the pilot network which of these needs we further want to develop into a prototype for capacity building material (prioritisation). We also wanted to discuss about the form in which we want to provide the content to the end user (training, guidelines, webinar, database, etc.).

The objective of WP6 was to understand how a virtual environment could support a European network and what the functionalities the Virtual Lab might include.

• *Approach*

The thematic working group discussions to operationalise the collaborative themes consisted out of a presentation of the five collaborative themes and their sub-topics followed by a discussion on the following questions:

- What are your expectations of the Thematic Working Groups?
- What do you think what is feasible to do by the end of the project? (September 2023)
Identification of actions in relation to the subtopics
- Who can do this? Assign members to the actions

After this members voted and created a priority list at the venue using flipcharts.

For the learning roundtable around best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders there was firstly a presentation of two inspiring examples from the pilot network on Best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders followed by a Q&A. Hereafter a peer assist exercise in two groups created a discussion on the following points:

- issue, problem or challenge faced by individual members in relation to co-creation and involving stakeholders
- viable solutions found by the group members

The exercise was closed with a plenary feedback moment.

For the workshop on the needs, challenges, and benefits of a future European network the key results of the needs, challenges, and benefits of the network from the interviews and previous meetings were presented, followed by a Q& A + group feedback and discussion on the results.

The exercise on the prototyping the CBP consisted of:

- 1) Presentation of results of 'scoping of the capacity building plan'/ questions
- 2) Prioritisation exercise:
 - a. Content: What would be the most interesting content for capacity building material for the members in your LL/RI? pilot network members had 3 voting sticky dots to prioritise main needs on a poster listing 'needs for capacity building'

Format: what would be the most interesting format to bring the content to the LL/RI members? Pilot network members had to draw a line from their sticky dote to a format of interest. (a list of potential formats was provided as well on the poster)

To work with the pilot network members on how a virtual environment can support a European network and on which functionalities of the Virtual Lab need to include, a presentation was prepared followed by a group discussion:

1. Results of the 1st pilot network meeting
2. Showing the analysis, linking needs & functionalities
3. Initial Value proposition (first version, future versions):
 - a. Visualisation – map, database, form, data management
 - b. Sharing documents - File sharing
 - c. Networking – Networking functionalities

3.11 Regional workshops part I

- *Date/period in time*

2 November 2022 in Seville (Spain), 17 November 2022 in Frankfurt (Germany), 24 November 2022 in Budapest (Hungary) and 2 December 2022 in Billund (Denmark)

- *Target audience*

Representatives of LLs, RIs and funding organisations. In total, 84 people participated in these workshops.

- *Objectives*

A first set of four workshops were organised by INRAE, in the frame of WP2 and in close collaboration with the WP4 partners. The purpose was to inform participants about ALL-Ready, the AGROECOLOGY partnership and its future European network of LLs and RIs, to raise awareness of the ongoing European-wide survey of LLs and RIs and to provide a platform for exchanging experiences and networking amongst local and regional actors. Within this context the discussion focussed on key themes in relation to challenges that LLs and RIs are facing in accelerating transitions to AE, including a reflection of funding issues and a first exploration of possible roles of a future European network of AE LLs and RIs in addressing those challenges.

- *Approach*

After a short introduction round and presentation of the ALL-Ready project, the future European network and the AGROECOLOGY partnership, the ALL-Ready online survey tool (<https://sondages.inrae.fr/index.php/458632>) was explained and illustrated to the participants. In the main part of the workshops, participants discussed questions related to the experiences of their LLs and RIs in accelerating transitions to AE. The participants debated

in two groups (participants at the venue and online participants) about the challenges and needs of their initiatives within the transition process, their views about the key contributions of a future European network and their potential role in it. The discussions captured insights from a range of LLs and RIs, some are mature and well-established over many years, while others are new and have only been recently set up, and facilitated learning from each other.

3.12 Third pilot network meeting

- *Date/period in time*

21-23 November 2022 in Budapest (Hungary)

- *Target audience*

Representatives of the members of the pilot network. In total, 22 people participated, a combination of project partners (10) and pilot network members (12).

- *Objectives*

The overall aim of the meeting was to build on the outcomes of the 1st and 2nd pilot meetings and continue the work started in WPs 3-4-5-6:

(1) to give an update on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members and to propose and agree on new tasks for the network (WP3);

(2) to learn about the use of three practical tools for co-creation to address the gap between scientists and farmers that the members can use in their own LL/RIs (WP3);

(3) to reflect on the main purpose of the future European network and to explore key issues for its governance that would help ensuring its long-term sustainability (WP4);

(4) to discuss and identify gaps in the first prototype of the CBP and the gathered capacity building materials (WP5);

(5) to train participants on the pre-operational version of the AE Virtual Lab and validate the current version of the platform (WP6);

- *Approach*

The 3rd pilot network meeting was organised by ÖMKi with support from WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 partners. The hybrid meeting was a combination of presentations and active workshop sessions, each organised and facilitated by WPs 3-4-5 and 6.

Presentations included an introduction to the ALL-Ready project and the AGROECOLOGY partnership by the project coordinator just as presentation on the achievements of the project by all WP leads. After that, the programme consisted of following workshop sessions:

WP3:

- validation session to give an update on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members, and to propose and agree on new tasks for the network;
- carousel brainstorm in 3 groups by situational exercises to learn about the implementation and use of tools for co-creation and stakeholder engagement to address the gap between scientists and farmers that they can use in their own LL/RIs.

WP4: workshop session to reflect on the key dimensions of the implementation plan for the future European network.

WP5: workshop session to present and discuss the first prototype of the CBP and to identify gaps in this prototype.

WP6: workshop session to train participants on the pre-operational version of the AE virtual lab and validate this version together with the participants.

Besides this, a field visit at Csoroszlya farm was organised on the final day of this 3-day event.

3.13 Interviews: develop an implementation plan for the future network

- *Date/period in time*

January - March 2023, virtually

- *Target audience*

16 representatives of networks of networks.

The criteria that were applied in selecting networks of networks for the interviews considered different types of initiatives and organisations that can represent a network of network, the geographic coverage and the main funding sources. Further selection criteria were applied in reviewing candidate initiatives included network governance, thematic focus and strategic focus.

- *Objectives*

The interviews were conducted in the frame of WP4 coordinated by TU and supported by WP4 project partners (INRAE, ECOLOGIC and BIOSENSE) with the objective to improve the understanding of key factors for the successful long-term implementation of the European network of AE LLs and RIs, by learning from the experiences of, and lessons from other networks of networks in the agriculture and rural development arena across Europe (and beyond).

- *Methodology*

16 semi-structured interviews made via phone or videoconference, based on a set of questions related to governance, funding, data management, capacity building cooperation as well as communication and dissemination.

3.14 Regional workshops part II

- *Date/period in time*

11 May 2023 in Seville (Spain), 12 May 2023 in Budapest (Hungary), 22 June 2023 in Frankfurt and the 29 September 2023 in Helsinki (Finland).

- *Target audience*

Local and regional actors involved in LLs and RIs and representatives of potential funding bodies. A total of 66 people participated in these workshops.

- *Objectives*

A second set of regional workshops were organised in the frame of WP4 by TU with support from other partners such as ECOLOGIC, OMKI, UOULU, and was mainly tailored to objectives in WP4 and WP5. They contributed to development of an implementation plan for the future network (WP4) and of recommendations for capacity building in the regions (WP5). More specifically, key objectives of the workshops were to:

- Discuss key dimensions of the implementation plan of a European network from the perspective of local and regional actors involved in LLs and RIs and their funding;
- Further raise awareness of the added value of the AGROECOLOGY partnership and the future European network as well as increasing the interest to engage in it;
- Provide a platform for exchanging and networking amongst local/regional actors.

- *Approach*

The workshop was organised in a hybrid format to allow participation also for those for whom travelling was not easy/impossible. The workshop started with an introductory presentation on the context and background for the discussion later on. It included an overview of some first insights in an implementation plan for the future network, including dimensions on thematic areas, funding, capacity building, communication and networking. In the discussion afterwards, groups of 10 people exchanged in 2 rounds of 1 hour on challenges they experience in each of these dimensions in order to support the transition to AE. They reflected on the potential contribution of the future network in dealing with these challenges to provide recommendations for the implementation plan of the future network.

3.15 Fourth pilot network meeting

- *Date/period in time*

14-16 June 2023, in Montpellier (France)

- *Target audience*

Representatives of the members of the pilot network. In total, 24 people participated. Among them 12 project partners and 12 pilot network members.

- *Objectives*

The 4th pilot network meeting was organised in the frame of WP3 by ÖMKi and INRAE-Montpellier with support from WP4, WP5 and WP6 partners. The overall objective was to facilitate peer to peer learning among the pilot network members, just as to co-create the framework for the future network of LL and RIs together with the project partners. More WP specific objectives were:

For WP3, a first objective was to introduce the AGROECOLOGY partnership and the future network and discuss continuation of the pilot network in the future network. A second objective was to identify recommendations for this future network based on the experiences of the pilot network.

For WP5, the objective was to test a prototype of a training on systems thinking and a prototype of a training on LL models, real-life experimentation and facilitation techniques. Feedback was gathered from the pilot network members.

For WP4, the objective was to introduce the concept, approach and structure of the implementation plan for the future network and to reflect on key issues of selected dimensions that the implementation plan needs to cover.

Finally, for WP6, the objective was to present and validate the last release of the AE Virtual Lab and to discuss principles for innovation management focused on data sharing and use and intellectual property rights.

- *Methodology*

The hybrid meeting was a combination of training and workshop sessions, each organised and facilitated by WPs 3-4-5 and 6.

The meeting consisted of 5 different sessions:

- Looking back & ahead: pilot network achievements, progress and the future;
- Joint reflection on pilot co-creation activities. The two sessions were organised by the WP3 team of ALL-Ready. The sessions were facilitated by Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) and May Hobeika (Ecologic) and supported by Valéria Csonka (ÖMKi) and Antonia Riedel (Ecologic) as notetakers.
- Capacity Building training sessions on: systems thinking and LL model, real-life experimentation & facilitation techniques. The systems thinking training was organised and facilitated by Jo Bijttebier (ILVO) and Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO). The LL model, real-life experimentation & facilitation techniques training session was organised by Isabelle Couture (ENOLL) and Dolinda Cavallo (ENOLL) and facilitated by Dimitri Schuurman and Gilles Wuyts from IMEC (interuniversity micro electronica centre) (<https://www.imec-int.com/en/about-us>).
- Developing an implementation plan for the European network. The session was organised and facilitated by Gerald Schwarz (TU) with support from Bastian Goldel (INRAE).
- Finalising the AE Virtual Lab and discussing innovation, data and IPR management. LifeWatch ERIC Technical Team organised and prepared the session: José Manuel Ávila Castuera (AE Coordinator), Iria Soto Embodas (AE Project Manager) and Daniel Caro Gómez (AE Services Integration Assistant). It was facilitated by José Manuel Ávila Castuera (LifeWatch ERIC) and supported by Iria Soto Embodas (LifeWatch ERIC) as notetaker.

The meeting workshops were combined with a field visit to one of the Open Labs (Open Lab VITI) of Occitanum Living Lab at Le Mas Numérique where members become acquainted with the testing and adoption of digital tools in AE, specifically in viticulture.

3.16 Workshop: validation of the capacity building program

- *Date/period in time*

22 September 2023, in Barcelona (Spain)

- *Target audience*

Representatives of the members of the pilot network. In total, 19 people participated, 11 people representing pilot network members and 8 people representing project partners.

- *Objectives*

This workshop was the final one of the CBP “Capacity Building for AE” and was organised during the Open Living Lab Days in Barcelona in the frame of the WP5 and WP3 activities by ENOLL and EV ILVO, with support from other partners. The primary objective was to bring together members of the pilot network offering them the opportunity to assess the progress made in the capacity building training sessions conducted thus far and to gather valuable insights for shaping the program's future direction. Additionally, this workshop facilitated the exchange of experiences among pilot network members through peer-to-peer exchange, with a particular focus on specific aspects of LL and RI management

- *Approach*

The workshop was organised around 2 timeslots allocated to each of both objectives. Small group discussions were organised to gather feedback on the CBP by focusing on “how to better adapt the capacity building training to AE sector/local context”. In a second round, peer to peer exchange was facilitated by 3 rounds of 3 rounds of peer consultation in groups of 4 people (round 1: stakeholder engagement, round 2: organisation of field visits, round 3: monitoring and evaluation of LL/Ris).

3.17 Final conference: Brussels

- *Date/period in time*

27 September 2023, in Brussels (Belgium)

- *Target audience*

All stakeholders involved in supporting AE transition through LLs and RIs, both at local, national and European (and even beyond) level. A total of 123 people participated.

- *Objectives*

The one-day conference was jointly organised by ALL-Ready, in the frame of WP7 and WP8, and AE4EU. From ALL-Ready, the main organisers were FIBL EU and INRAE, although all partners contributed. The event shed light on how the two projects paved the way for a European network of AE LLs and RIs. Both projects featured stories from the field, pilot network and local stakeholders. Experiences from involved LLs and RIs gave practical insights on the AE transition in Europe.

- *Methodology*

Through a series of panel discussions, the event explored how LLs and RIs can support the AE transition. LL and RIs shared inspiring experiences on how to translate theory into practice and how to put AE LLs and RIs in practice. This and related questions were at the forefront of participatory discussions to understand lessons learned from three years of project work.

The closing session focused on how regions can best support LLs and Ris to drive the AE and urban transitions. The role of local authorities and the future AGROECOLOGY partnership were given prime consideration.

4. Evaluation of stakeholder engagement

While many stakeholder activities aim at informing, consulting, involving or cocreating with stakeholders, it is important to understand what is the impact of these activities. A thorough

evaluation can provide important lessons learned that are crucial, most of all for setting up the future network of AE LLs and RIS, but also for elaborating future projects with stakeholders or stakeholder management in general.

Because this evaluation task is so essential, a whole deliverable is dedicated to this: D3.3 *Booklet on overall stakeholder recommendations for the implementation of the future European Agroecology LL and RI network*, which gathered the lessons learnt and recommendations for stakeholder engagement for the implementation of the future European network of AE LLs and RIs. We would like to refer to that document for understanding the evaluation of the stakeholder activities.

References

Ackermann, F. and Eden, C. (2011). Strategic Management of stakeholders: Theory and Practice. Long Range Planning, 44: 179-196.

Muriel Mambrini-Doudet, M., Gascuel, C., Göldel, B., McKhann, H. (2021). D1.1 Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition. ALL-Ready Deliverable.

Freeman, R.E., 1984. Strategic Management: a Stakeholder Approach. Pitman Publishing, Marshfield, Mass. 60 p.

Green, A.O. and Hunton-Clarke, L. (2003). A typology of stakeholder participation for company environmental decision-making. Business Strategy and the Environment, 12: 292-299.

Haller, L. (2021). D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan. ALL-Ready Deliverable.

Reed, M.S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C.H., Stringer, L.C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. Journal of Environmental Management, 90: 1933-1949.

Wilcox D. 1994. The Guide to Effective Participation. Partnership: Brighton.